

References

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Interaction of 4, 5-Dimethoxyhomophthalic Anhydride with Phthalic Anhydride : Synthesis of 6, 7-Dimethoxy-3-(2-Carboxy)-Phenylisocoumarins and Related Substances :

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APPPLICATION of the phthaloylation reaction¹ with phthalic anhydride in pyridine to 4, 5-dimethoxyhomophthalic anhydride (I) gave directly 4-carboxy-6, 7-dimethoxy-3-(2-carboxyphenyl) isocoumarin (II) in good yield, the reaction having taken place in the same manner as already explained in case of homophthalic and 4-methoxyhomophthalic anhydrides¹.

The investigations on the 4-carboxyisocoumarin (II) as depicted in the chart have led to easy synthesis of the isocoumarin (III), the 3,4-dihydroisocoumarin (VII) and the other related substances that are of importance particularly because of the methoxy groups in position 6 and 7, commonly found in natural products.

Experimental

4, 5-Dimethoxyhomophthalic anhydride (I) : It was prepared by refluxing 4,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid² (5 g.) with acetic anhydride (10 ml) for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The crystals separated on cooling were washed with ether and sublimed under reduced pressure to obtain the anhydride (4 g), m.p. 175°-76°. (Found : C, 59.7 ; H, 4.4 ; C₁₁H₁₀O₅ requires C, 59.9 and H, 4.5%).

4-Carboxy-6, 7-dimethoxy-3-(2-carboxyphenyl) isocoumarin (II) : 4, 5-Dimethoxyhomophthalic anhydride (I, 1 g), phthalic anhydride (1.5 g) and dry pyridine (6 ml) were mixed and stirred for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. and left at room temperature overnight. The reaction mixture was then poured on crushed ice containing dil. HCl and was allowed to stand for 2 hrs. The separated solid crystallised from acetic acid as shining cubes, m. p. 258° (decomp), yield 1.4 g. (Found : C, 61.3 ; H, 4.2. C₁₉H₁₄O₈ requires C, 61.6 and H, 3.8%). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 245 nm (log ϵ : 4.59).

When however the same reaction was carried out at the temperature of boiling water bath for 3 hr and the product (1.3 g, m. p. 210-25°) was boiled with methanol (25 ml) only a part went into solution. The insoluble part yielded II (0.55 g) while the methanolic solution on concentration (charcoal) and cooling afforded the isocoumarin III (0.55 g) described below.

The anhydride (IX): The anhydride (IX) was formed by refluxing II (0.5 g) with acetic anhydride (15 ml) or by stirring a mixture of III (0.5 g), acetic anhydride (5 ml) and pyridine (few drops) in ether as solvent at room temperature. The product crystallised from dioxane as yellowish silky needles, m. p. 270°-71°, yield 0.35 g. (Found : C, 64.4; H, 3.8. C₁₉H₁₂O₇ requires C, 64.77 and H, 3.4%).

6,7-Dimethoxy-3-(2-carboxyphenyl) isocoumarin (III): The dicarboxyisocoumarin (II) (0.5 g) was heated in a metal bath at 258° for 3 to 4 min. (evolution of CO₂). The contents were boiled with water (5 ml) and the supernatant decanted off. Aq. NaHCO₃ extract of the residue on acidification gave a solid that crystallised from methanol as silky needles, m.p. 240-41°; yield 0.3 g. (Found C, 65.8; H, 4.3. C₁₈H₁₄O₆ requires : C, 66.27; H, 4.3%). λ_{max}^{MeOH} 242, 270, 310 nm (log ε : 4.53, 4.43, 4.21),

The methyl ester (IV): The methyl ester (IV) was prepared by refluxing III (1g) with methanol (60 ml) and conc. H₂SO₄ (1 ml) for 3 hr. The ester crystallised from ethyl acetate as needles, m.p. 163-64°, yield 0.8 g (Found: C, 66.7; H, 5.0. C₁₉H₁₆O₆ requires C, 67.05; H, 4.7 %).

2-Carboxy-4, 5-dimethoxybenzyl-12-carboxyphenyl ketone (VI): The isocoumarin (II or III) (1 g) was mixed with aq. NaOH (10 ml, 10%) and was left at room temperature for 10-15 min. The solution on acidification gave a solid that crystallised from ethyl acetate as cubes, m.p. 234°-35° (decomp.); yield 0.8 g. (Found : C, 63.3; H, 4.7. C₁₈H₁₆O₇ requires C, 62.8; H, 4.7%). The anhydride IX afforded VI on refluxing with aq. NaOH.

The ketone VI (1 g.) on keeping with H₂SO₄ (2.5 ml, 90%) and usual work up, gave isocoumarin III (0.8 g)

6, 7-Dimethoxy-3-phenylisocoumarin (V): The decarboxylation of II (0.5 g) was carried out exactly in the same procedure described before¹. The product crystallised from benzene as silky needles (0.3 g.) m.p. 165-66° (Found : C, 72.01; H, 5.0 C₁₇H₁₄O₄ requires C, 72.45; H, 4.9%). λ_{max}^{MeOH} 230, 270 and 320 nm (log ε : 4.31, 4.61, 4.27).

6,7-Dimethoxy-3-(2-carboxyphenyl)-3, 4-dihydroisocoumarin (VII): To the methanolic solution of the ketone VI (0.5 g), NaBH₄ (0.5 g) was added in small portions at room temperature with shaking. Usual work up and crystallisations from ethanol yielded VII (0.4 g) as needles, m.p. 222°-23° (decomp.); (Found : C, 65.4; H, 4.7. C₁₈ H₁₆O₆ requires C, 65.87; H, 4.87%). λ_{max}^{MeOH} 224, 255 nm (log ε : 4.64, 4.08).

6, 7-Dimethoxy-3, 4-dihydroisocoumarin-3, 3'-spiropthalide (VIII): The ketone VI (1 g) was boiled with conc. HCl (30 ml) for 1 hr. On cooling the solid was filtered and washed with aq. NaHCO₃ and then with water. It crystallised from ethyl acetate as needles, m.p. 250°-52°; yield 0.8 g. (Found C, 66.5; H, 4.2; C₁₈H₁₄O₆ requires C, 66.3; H, 4.3%), λ_{max}^{MeOH} 225, 270, 302 nm (log ε 4.59, 4.15, 3.94).

The above spiropthalide on heating with aq. NaOH (10%) on water bath and subsequent acidification with conc. HCl regenerated the ketone (VI).

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Formation of 1-Aroyl-2, 3-Phthaloylpyrrocolines

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It has already been reported¹ from this laboratory that the condensation product of 2,3-dichloronaphthoquinone with isochroman-1, 4-dione in presence of hot pyridine was really 1-(0-carboxylbenzoyl)-2,3-phthaloylpyrrocoline (Ia) instead of 7,12-dihydro-5,7, 12-trioxo-5H-naphtho (2',3': 4,3) furo (3,2-c) isochromen (II) as suggested by Buu-Hoi *et al.*²

II

- Ia, R = R₁ = R₂ = H
 Ib, R = H, R₁ = R₂ = OCH₃
 Ic, R = R₂ = H, R₁ = OCH₃
 Id, R = CH₃, R₁ = R₂ = OCH₃
 Ie, R = CH₃, R₂ = H, R₁ = OCH₃

In the present communication it is intended to record some more examples of this type of condensation leading to pyrrocolines (I) to reinforce the previous conclusion. Thus, the condensation of 2,3-dichloronaphthoquinone with 6,7-dimethoxyisochroman-1,4 dione³ in hot pyridine led to the pyrrocoline (Ib) which was converted to its ester (Id). The acid (Ib) when degraded with alkaline potassium permanganate gave α-picolinic acid detected by colour test with cyanogen bromide and β-naphthylamine⁴. The mass spectrum of the ester was